

Phytochemical Screening of *Ocimum gratissimum L*

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Abstract

Phytochemical screening revealed presence of tannins, saponins, alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids and cardenolides. One well-know herb that is utilized in Indian medicine is *Ocimum gratissimum*. According to folk medicine, it can help headaches, fevers, diarrhea, pneumonia, and other ailments. The majority of the claims are supported by research conducted utilizing various in vitro biological evaluation approaches. In this review, the chemistry of natural products, information about the plants pharmacological clinical, and toxicological properties.

Key words: *Ocimum gratissimum*, antifungal, phytochemical, screening

Introduction

Ocimum gratissimum L is a perennial and sub-shrub. It belongs to the family Lamiaceae and originated from Eastern India, and expanded to almost every tropical region on Earth [1]. Numerous ethnopharmacological surveys have documented *Ocimum gratissimum L* as a plant that is easily accessible to the people and commonly utilized in traditional medicine. This shrub is frequently found around gardens and village cottages [2,3]. The Igbo-speaking peoples of

Nigeria refer to it as Nchanwu, Dadoya in Hausa, Ebavbokho in Bini, and Efinrin nla inyoruba [4]. It is referred to as Omujaja in Ugaanda [3]. Numerous pharmacological and phytochemical investigations of *O gratissimum L* leaves have revealed the abundance of solvent and oil extract in bioactive phytochemicals. Reports have demonstrated its ability to detoxify the liver and its antioxidant properties [5,6]. Its essential oil antibacterial antifungal, and anti-inflammatory qualities have been amply shown [7,8,9]. It has been demonstrated that *Ocimum* oil can soothe irritated gastrointestinal tracts in cases of diarrhea [10] shown that the plant crude extract inhibited the growth and angiogenesis of breast tumours.

The majority of aches and pains are caused by inflammation, a silent invader. There is strong experimental, pathological, and epidemiological evidence that inflammation is the cause of the majority of crippling illnesses, including obesity and other age-related conditions. Rheumatoid arthritis, cancer, metabolic syndrome, and neurodegenerative illnesses [12]. The largest cause of suffering and financial burden worldwide is attributed to inflammatory illnesses which impact a large number of individuals. It has been demonstrated that anti-inflammatory herbal medications and their ingredients are effective defences against a variety of pro-inflammatory mediators of inflammation, both acute and chronic. Despite the pharmaceutical and herbal industries increasing interest in plants extract anti-inflammatory properties, a large percentage of plant species studied in detail in figure [1] [13].

In this study, our goal was to test the hydroethanolic extract of *O gratissimum* leaves anti-inflammatory properties in vitro.

Figure- 1: Collection of *Ocimum gratissimum L* Plants.

2: Materials and methods

Collection and identification of plant materials

Fresh leaves of *Ocimum gratissimum* Plants (collected in November, 2024 from different locations) from Krishi Vigyan Kendra (KVK).

3: Preparation of plant materials

Dried plant materials were extracted with methanol (cold extraction) for maceration, 5g of dry material was dissolved in 80% of methanol and then kept in water bath shaker for an hour shaken continuously for an hour and filtered through (Whatman No.1). filter paper. The filtrate was used for screening and qualitative tests to find out if any particular phytochemicals were present. Carbohydrate test (Moliesh test, Fehling test, Benedict test, Anthron test), Flavonoids test, protein test, Tannins test, steroids test, saponin test and phenol test.

4: Phytochemical screening

Evans description of conventional standard practices [16], Harborne [17], Odebiyi and sofawora [18] or identifying the various chemical components present in the plant extract were used. Alkaloids, anthraquinones, tannins, saponins, flavonoids, cardenolides, and terpenoids are among the secondary metabolites that examined. The compounds existence evaluated as either negative (-) or positive (+) in Table 1. The phytochemical screening of the plant extract using carried out by testing class of compounds using standards methods. An essential technique in the analysis of bioactive compounds, the phytochemical, screening assay is a quick, easy, and affordable process that provides the researcher with an immediate response to the many kinds of phytochemicals present in a combination. assay, a crucial method for analyzing bioactive chemicals, is a quick, simple, and reasonably priced procedure that gives the researcher an instant

Table-1: phytochemicals in methanolic and aqueous leaf extract of *Ocimum gratissimum L*

Phytochemicals	Methanolic extracts	Aqueous extracts
Alkaloids	+	-
Saponins	-	+
Tannins	+	+
Phlobatannins	+	+
Anthraquinones	-	+
Steroids	+	+
Terpenoids	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+
Cardiac glycosides		
With steroidal ring	+	+
With deoxy – sugar	-	+

+ = Present

- = Absent

5. Result and Discussion

Phytochemical screening results

The results revealed the presence of saponins, alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, cardenolides and terpenoids. But deoxy-sugar with methanolic extract. The ethanolic extract contains flavonoids and tannins, according to the phytochemical screening. Estimations to flavonoid contents showed a considerable level of total polyphenolics in the hydro-ethanolic extract. Previous research has indicated that *O. gratissimum* leaves are non-phlobatannins and essential oil. the main volatile oil components of *O. gratissimum* were eugenol, thymol, and geraniol.

6. Conclusion

The plant *Ocimum gratissimum* screening, natural products and pharmacology, and clinical investigations have been discussed in this paper. The plant *o.gratissimum* possesses has a lot of promise and helps with a variety of illnesses. Therefore, this paper will be helpful to researcher's who want to validate the undiscovered truth that hasn't been confirmed by science.

7. References

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